

Development of AGBNP2 Implicit Solvent Model Library for MD Simulations

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Abstract

We developed a library for implicit solvent calculation according to the AGBNP2 implicit solvent model prescription. The library implements the calculation of solvent forces as well as energy of solvation for adaptation in molecular dynamics simulations. The preliminary results are very encouraging. The library performance is good, indicating it as desirable future to integrate classical MD codes such as DL_POLY and GROMACS.

1. Introduction

Water plays a fundamental role in virtually all biological processes. The fundamental quantity that implicit solvent models for water seek to approximate is the solute potential of mean force, which determines the statistical weight of solute conformations, and which is obtained by averaging over the solvent degrees of freedom [1].

Atomistic models of solvated bio-molecules need to include some description of water-solute interactions in order to achieve at least qualitative level of fidelity. There is a variety of approaches used to model solvation effects. Amongst these the implicit solvent models (ISMs) take a central place. They consider the solution as a continuous medium often described by macroscopic parameters such as density, dielectric permittivity and surface tension. ISMs take a variety of forms and although they are an approximate version of the explicit models they are often a much desired alternative due to their much lower computational cost with respect to that of the explicit models.

“The AGBNP2 implicit solvent model, an evolution of the Analytical Generalized Born plus Non-Polar (AGBNP) model we have previously reported, is presented with the aim of modeling hydration effects beyond those described by conventional continuum dielectric representations. A new empirical hydration free energy component based on a procedure to locate and score hydration sites on the solute surface is introduced to model first solvation shell effects, such as hydrogen bonding, which are poorly described by continuum dielectric models. This new component is added to the Generalized Born and non-polar AGBNP terms. Also newly introduced is an analytical Solvent Excluded Volume (SEV) model which improves the solute volume description by reducing the effect of spurious high-dielectric interstitial spaces present in conventional van der Waals representations. The AGBNP2 model is parametrised and tested with respect to experimental hydration free energies of small molecules and the results of explicit solvent simulations. Modeling the granularity of water is one of the main design principles employed for the first shell solvation function and the SEV model, by requiring that water locations have a minimum available volume based on the size of a water molecule. It is shown that the new volumetric model produces Born radii and surface areas in good agreement with accurate numerical evaluations of these quantities.”[3]

We do not include all formulae implemented in the AGBNP2 library we developed and we advise the reader to have a look at [2] and [3] in case of interest in the complete model derivation.

The solute is modeled using Gaussian overlap approach and its volume computed using Poincare formula. The volume of a set of intersecting elements is

$$V'_i = V_i - \frac{1}{2} \sum_j V_{ij} + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i < j} V_{ijk} + \dots, \quad (1)$$

where $V_i = 4/3\pi R_i^3$ is the volume of atom i , V_{ij} is the volume intersection of atoms i and j (second order intersection), V_{ijk} is the volume of intersection of atoms i, j , and k (third order intersection), and so on. The total volume of the molecule is

$$V = \sum_i V'_i. \quad (2)$$

The overlap volume formed by n spheres is then approximated by the integral of the product of the n corresponding Gaussian functions:

$$V_{12\dots n}^g = p_{12\dots n} \exp(-K_{12\dots n}) \left(\frac{\pi}{\Delta_{12\dots n}} \right)^{3/2}, \quad (3)$$

where the coefficients p , K and Δ are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{12\dots n} &= p^n \\ p &= \frac{4\pi}{3} \left(\frac{\kappa}{\pi} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \\ K_{12\dots n} &= \frac{1}{\Delta_{12\dots n}} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=i+1}^n c_i c_j r_{ij}^2 \\ \Delta_{12\dots n} &= \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \\ c_i &= \frac{\kappa}{R_i^2}; \kappa = 2.227. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

From a computational point of view one has to work with the intersection values computed by formulae below

$$V_{12\dots n} = \begin{cases} 0 & :: V_{12\dots n}^g \leq v_1 \\ V_{12\dots n}^g f_w(u) & :: v_1 < V_{12\dots n}^g < v_2 \\ V_{12\dots n}^g & :: V_{12\dots n}^g \geq v_2 \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

where v_1 and v_2 are predefined constants, u is

$$u = \frac{V_{12\dots n}^g - v_1}{v_2 - v_1}, \quad (6)$$

and the function f_w is

$$f_w(x) = x^3(10 - 15x + 6x^2). \quad (7)$$

The atomic surface can be calculated if one differentiates the atomic volume with respect to the atomic radius, R_i ,

$$A_i = f_a \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial R_i} \right), \quad (8)$$

where f_a is a function ensuring the positivity of A as:

$$f_a(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x^3}{a^2 + x^2} & :: x > 0 \\ 0 & :: x \leq 0 \end{cases}. \quad (9)$$

The hydration free energy is represented as a sum of electrostatic, non-polar and hydrogen bonding terms in AGBNP2 model:

$$\Delta_h G = \Delta G_{elec} + \Delta G_{np} + \Delta G_{hb} . \quad (10)$$

The non-polar term consist of terms describing cavity formation energy, ΔG_{cav} , and van der Waals interaction energy, ΔG_{vdw} , with solvent molecules.

$$\Delta G_{cav} = \sum_i \gamma_i A_i , \quad (11)$$

where γ_i is the surface tension parameter assigned to atom i and A_i is van der Waals surface area.

$$\Delta G_{vdw} = \sum_i \frac{\alpha_i a_i}{(B_i + R_w)^3} , \quad (12)$$

where α_i is an adjustable dimensionless parameter on the order of 1 and

$$a_i = -\frac{16}{3} \pi \rho_w \epsilon_{iw} \sigma_{iw}^6 , \quad (13)$$

where ρ_w is the number density of water at standard conditions, σ_{iw} and ϵ_{iw} are the Lennard-Jones parameters for the interaction between atom i . and an oxygen atom of the water model.

The Born radius B_i of a solute atom is calculated from

$$B_i^{-1} = f_b(\beta_i) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{b^2 + \beta_i^2} & :: \beta > 0 \\ b & :: \beta_i \leq 0 \end{cases} . \quad (14)$$

Again, the function $f_b(\beta)$ keeps the result finite. Its parameter β_i is calculated using the volume scaling s_{ij} and the pair de-screening functions Q_{ij}

$$\beta_i = \frac{1}{R_i} - \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{i \neq j} s_{ij} Q_{ij} . \quad (15)$$

The volume scaling factor is calculated as

$$s_{ij} = s_j + \frac{V'_{ij}}{V_j} , \quad (16)$$

where V_j is the atomic volume without correction and V'_{ij} is the cross-section volume of atoms i and j calculated as

$$V'_{ji} = V'_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} V_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} \sum_k V_{ijk} + \frac{1}{4} \sum_{k < l} V_{ijkl} - \dots , \quad (17)$$

and s_j is calculated as

$$s_j = \frac{V'_j - d_j A_j}{V_j} , \quad (18)$$

where

$$d_j = \frac{1}{3} R'_j \left[1 - \left(\frac{R_j}{R'_j} \right)^3 \right] . \quad (19)$$

and R'_j is the augmented radius:

$$R' = R + dR , \quad (20)$$

with dR taken as 0.5 Å.

2. Library development

We have implemented AGBNP2 library as following the main ideas as proposed in [1]. Namely, to construct second, third and fourth order volumes and store only those doublets, triplets and quadruplets where cross-volumes calculated from eqn.(5) are greater than zero. The next step is to calculate atomic volumes according to eqn.(1) and eqn.(8). The last two quantities are stored in arrays of length equal to the number of atoms.

In order to save computational time we decided to calculate the quantities defined by eqns.(14,18,19) and store them in the memory taking into account the fact that the values are need many times during hydration free energy and resulting forces calculation. The last mentioned quantities except second order cross-section values V'_{ij} in eqn.(17) are stored in one dimensional arrays, while for storing V'_{ij} we use a B-tree.

V'_{ij} B-tree: The basic object with B-tree constituents are nodes. In our implementation a node object has the following data members:

- 10 pointers of type node
- *level* – an integer type scalar
- *dimid* – an integer type scalar
- *connected* – an integer array of length 10: with value of -1 if the node is not connected, 0 for connected state and greater than 0 if the node has *level*=1 and *dimid* is set to the last dimension then the value is the number of the floating number in the values array (see below).

Figure 1. A schematic representation of V'_{ij} B-tree connectivity.

The B-tree object itself describes all data stored in the tree. It has:

- *ndims* – an integer type scalar holding the number of the dimensions of the indices

- *maxlevel* – an integer type scalar holding the maximum number of levels along dimensions
- *maxdata* – an integer type scalar holding the maximum number of floating point numbers that can be stored by the tree
- *ndata* – an integer type scalar holding the number of data already stored in the *values* array
- *values* – double precision floating point data array
- *root_node* – pointer of type node

The main idea is presented schematically in Figure 1. The top node has *level*=*maxlevel* and *dimid*=1. The *dimid* value is the number of the index dimension and the *level* value is the number of the digit of the index number in decimal representation.

For example, let us have floating point numbers mapped to two dimensional indices (i.e. pairs of indices) and say 25.6 is the floating number mapped to the {12;495} pair of indices (or two dimensional index). For *maxlevel*=4 the nodes in the tree mapping the mentioned floating point number will have the following attributes:

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root_node: level=4; dimid=1; connected(1)=0; n0->nodeadd1
node [nodeadd1] : level=3; dimid=1; connected(1)=0; n0->nodeadd2
node [nodeadd2] : level=2; dimid=1; connected(2)=0; n1->nodeadd3
node [nodeadd3] : level=1; dimid=1; connected(3)=0; n2->nodeadd4
node [nodeadd4] : level=4; dimid=2; connected(1)=0; n0->nodeadd5
node [nodeadd5] : level=3; dimid=2; connected(5)=0; n4->nodeadd6
node [nodeadd6] : level=2; dimid=2; connected(10)=0; n9->nodeadd7
node [nodeadd7] : level=1; dimid=2; connected(6)=321;n5->NULL
values(321)=25.6

```

Once the V'_{ij} are calculated and stored they are used for on-the-fly calculation of the atomic scaling factors s_{ij} wherever needed. The rest of the coefficients and variables needed for this ISM scheme are calculated and stored in the memory for faster evaluation of the atomic forces due to the solvent continuum. For more information on these quantities the reader is referred to references [1,2] where the gradients of the solvation free energy are derived.

For better optimised OpenMP parallelisation we defined private copies of the number of doublets, triplets and quadruplets, including the doublets, triplets and quadruplets themselves as well as the private V'_{ij} B-trees for every one of the threads without data overlapping. While the atomic parameters like those defined by eqn.(13,18,19) as well as the atomic forces are shared between the threads. The main goal of the so implemented parallel algorithm is to loop over private mutliplets or to use parallel DO loops over shared data.

Scalability test

A test program was developed to examine the performance scalability of the library. It proceeds as follows:

1. Load atomic coordinates from a file and create neighbor lists for each of the atoms within a predefined cutoff (we used 5 Å).
2. Allocate necessary memory.
3. Load Lennard-Jones potential parameters from a file.
4. Constants initialization.
5. Calculate 2nd order cross-section volumes and store doublets.

6. Calculate 3rd order cross-section volumes and store triplets.
7. Calculate 4th order cross-section volumes and store quadruplets.
8. Calculate and store atomic SASA (Solvent accessible surface area) and atomic volumes.
9. Calculate and store scaling factors d_j and s_j – eqn.(18) and eqn.(19) respectively.
10. Calculate and store atomic Born radii.
11. Calculate free energy of solvation.
12. Calculate and store Y_i (see reference [2]).
13. Calculate and store U_i (see reference [2]).
14. Calculate and store W_i (see reference [2]).
16. Calculate atomic forces.
17. Free up the allocated memory.

The program library performance was tested on systems with sizes of 362, 4190, 7502 and 13796 atoms (inclusive of hydrogen atoms). Timing data shown in Table 1 represent the execution times for steps from 4 to 17 on a computer system with 2 CPUs Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5649@2.53GHz with HT enabled.

Table 1 Execution time v/s number of threads for different system sizes.

System size		362		4190		7502		13796	
[number of atoms]									
Number of threads	Execution time [ms]	Speedup							
1	10.99	1.00	152.02	1.00	272.69	1.00	506.08	1.00	
2	6.60	1.67	84.01	1.81	147.82	1.84	273.33	1.85	
3	4.27	2.57	72.18	2.11	115.77	2.36	186.45	2.71	
4	3.50	3.14	44.96	3.38	81.52	3.34	146.05	3.47	
5	3.15	3.49	38.04	4.00	69.45	3.93	130.59	3.88	
6	2.66	4.13	33.57	4.53	62.25	4.38	112.17	4.51	
7	2.41	4.57	28.60	5.32	55.31	4.93	100.11	5.06	
8	2.25	4.88	26.32	5.78	52.78	5.17	90.91	5.57	
9	2.26	4.86	24.97	6.09	49.60	5.50	89.31	5.67	
10	2.04	5.38	24.51	6.20	44.49	6.13	80.53	6.28	
11	2.10	5.24	24.51	6.20	42.83	6.37	77.83	6.50	
12	2.04	5.40	24.45	6.22	42.30	6.45	73.81	6.86	

As it is seen in Figure 2 the speedup for 12 threads is approximately 6. The execution time depends linearly on the system size and is independent on the number of threads as seen in Figure 3. It is worth mentioning that the execution time on 12 threads is less than 100 ms for all systems. The execution time for the 362 atoms is less than 11 ms.

Figure 2. Speedup as a function of the number of threads for systems of different size.

Figure 3. Execution time as a function of the system size for different number of threads.

3. Conclusion

We have developed an OpenMP version of the implicit solvent AGBNP2 model library. It is worth mentioning that no optimization of the free parameters of the model was made and thus such must be planned in the near future. The code scales well up to 12 threads according to the tests. The library performance scales linearly with the size of the system. Taking into account the achieved performance the library can be adapted and used for solvent forces evaluation in implicit solvent molecular dynamics simulations.

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References:

1. *Implicit solvent models*, B. Roux and T. Simonson, *Biophysical Chemistry* **78** 1-20 (1999).
2. *AGBNP: An Analytic Implicit Solvent Model*, E. Gallicchio and R.M. Levy, *J. Comput. Chem.* **25**(4) 479-499 (2004).
3. *The AGBNP2 Implicit Solvation Model*, E. Gallicchio, K. Paris and R.M. Levy *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **5**(9), 2544–2564 (2009).